

Use of Palmer's Technique as Primary Access Point in Surgery for Appendicular Lump and Difficult Appendicitis

Dipan. M. Kosambi¹, Smruti Ranjan Hota², Debashis Nanda³, Biranchi Narayan Lenka⁴

¹2nd Year PG, Department of General Surgery, Hi-Tech Medical College, Bhubaneswar (Odisha), India

²Asso. Prof. Department of General Surgery, Hi-Tech Medical College, Rourkela (Odisha), India

³2nd Year PG, Department of General Surgery, Hi-Tech Medical College, Bhubaneswar (Odisha), India

⁴Prof. Department of General Surgery, Hi-Tech Medical College, Bhubaneswar (Odisha), India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Biranchi Narayan Lenka

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Abstract:

It's commonly observed the appendicular mass/lump presentation in a patient with delayed presentation of appendicitis. And sequel of this mass/lump is gangrene, perforation, or abscess formation. As it has been found in multiple studies, the early surgical intervention results in reduced complicated sequel. Thus here we are discussing the use of Palmer's entry technique as the primary access point so as it gives the enhanced visualization of intraabdominal structures as well as avoiding injuries to the abdominal organs, which can be encountered in paraumbilical as primary access point approach. Total of 15 patients were diagnosed with appendicular lump/mass, clinically as well as with radiological diagnosis between the period of MARCH 2024 to JUNE 2024. Those all patients were managed by surgical intervention that is Laparoscopic Appendicectomy, with Palmer's point as the primary access point.

Keywords: Palmer's point, Appendicular lump, Appendicular mass, Palmer's access technique.

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Introduction

Appendicitis is the most common and frequently occurring acute abdomen causing surgical pathology [1]. Acute appendicitis can, at times, be contained by the body's natural defense mechanisms, leading to the inflammatory lump/mass aka appendiceal phlegmon or a circumcised abscess aka appendiceal abscess formation causing a palpable mass after the days of onset of symptoms. Occurrence rate of this complication is around 2%-7% of all cases of appendicitis [2,3]. The surgical treatment for the mentioned complication is surgical management. Surgical treatments are laparoscopic [4,5] or open appendicectomy [6], but latest accepted modality is laparoscopic surgical intervention. Thus hereby the laparoscopic appendicectomy was done in 15 cases with appendicular lump/mass in radiological findings as well as felt of mass/lump in right iliac fossa on palpation. For better visualization, of the entire lower right abdominal region Palmer's point [7] is used as the primary access site. Followed by 'Diamond Baseball' concept [8] used for working ports and 60% manipulation achieved for the surgery.

The aim of this study was to determine the efficiency of using Palmer's Point as the primary access site in the laparoscopic appendicectomy in case of appendicular mass/lump.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted at Hi-Tech Medical College and Hospital, Rourkela during the period of March 2024 to June 2024. During the mentioned period patients with diagnosis of appendiceal mass/lump were treated surgically. Appendiceal mass/lump is inflammatory tumor containing inflamed appendix, as well as adjacent viscera and greater omentum, while abscess is pus containing appendiceal mass. Patients were diagnosed primarily by physical examination, followed by radiological investigations, like CECT (contrast enhanced computed tomography) and ultrasound. Out of 15 patients 10 males and 5 females were treated with laparoscopic appendicectomy. The patients were pre-operatively assessed and prepared for laparoscopic appendicectomy. Patients were operated under general anaesthesia.

The primary access was done with Palmer's point. That is the tip of the left index finger is placed over the xiphisternum and the thumb is placed over anterior axillary line, now the mid-point of this is the palmer's point (i.e. approx. 3.5cm below costal margin in mid-clavicular line).

Figure 1: Identifying the Palmer's Point.

Figure 1.2: Veeres Needle insertion

Figure 1.3: Insufflation with Co2

Figure 1.4: 10mm Trocar Insertion.

After the port insertion at Palmer's point. Camera scope is introduced which gives an enhanced view of the intra-abdomen contents preventing injury to any organs, due to inflammation, as follows.

Figure 2

Figure 2.1

Figure 2.2

Figure 2.3

Figure 2.4

Then under the vision and as per the diamond ball concept the other 2 working ports were inserted giving the manipulation angle of 60° degree. These two ports are placed in contralateral positions as follows.

Figure 3: Using Diamond ball concept rest working ports inserted.

Figure 3.1: All 3 ports placed.

Thus using the Palmer's Point as primary access point in complicated appendicitis case the Laparoscopic surgery was performed as it was easy to appreciate the anatomy of the organs in the right lower quadrant of abdomen.

Results

Among the 15 patients, 10 males and 5 females were treated, among which 3 males had appendicular abscess, 5 males had inflamed appendicular lump and 2 males had gangrenous perforated appendix. While 3 females had inflamed appendicular lump, 1 had gangrenous perforated appendix and 1 had appendicular abscess. All were treated laparoscopically, decreasing the probability of converting into open surgery due to enhanced intra-abdominal view, and had satisfactory outcome, post op pain and prone to SSI reduced, along with reduced hospital stay, early enteral feeding started.

Discussion

Appendicitis and its complications are one of the commonest health issue in the developing world. Appendicular mass ^[9] is made up of spectrum of conditions. The appendix might be surrounded by the omentum, oedematous caecal wall, sigmoid colon, terminal ileum, or coils of the intestine surrounding the appendix which may enclose the inflamed appendix. The mass can be complicated with abscess formation commonly follows the appendicular perforation [10]. Although the interval appendicectomy [11,12,13] is advised treatment plan for adults in case of appendicular mass/lump. By adapting Palmer's point [14] as a primary access point, the major resection and anastomosis surgeries like hemicolectomies can also be performed in the same sitting.

As this case series report regarding surgical treatment of appendiceal mass is retrospective. From our point of view, prospective randomized controlled trails are required. We believe that prospec-

tive research concerning comparison of laparoscopic surgery with Palmer's technique as the primary access point and conservative treatment with interval surgery has great importance. Those studies will answer a lot of questions. According to the scientists' view, additional research is needed for fully understanding this subject.

Conclusions

Imaging techniques like CT (computed tomography) scans, are important to confirm the diagnosis of patients with suspected appendiceal mass and abscess. According to our report, we can conclude that laparoscopic appendicectomy with Palmer's technique of appendiceal mass and abscess have the better outcome. The surgeon must consider clinical symptoms and investigation-based results for choosing appropriate treatment methods in each particular case. Prospective randomized controlled trials are required for comparing the results of surgical and conservative treatment with interval surgery of appendiceal mass.

Declaration of competing interest: The authors declare no competing interest.

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